

An Assessment of Impact of Adaptive Notch Filters for Interference Removal on the Signal Processing Stages of a GNSS Receiver

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Abstract—With the fast growing diffusion of the real-time high accuracy applications based on the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), the robustness of the GNSS receiver performance has become a compelling requirement. Disruptive effects can be induced to the signal processing stages of GNSS receivers due to the disturbances from Radio-Frequency Interference (RFI), even leading to a complete outage of the positioning and timing service. A typical RFI threat to the GNSS signals is represented by portable jammers which transmit swept-frequency (chirp) signals in order to span the overall GNSS bandwidth. The implementation in the receivers of Adaptive Notch Filters (ANFs) for chirp cancellation has been extensively investigated and proved to be an efficient countermeasure. However, the performance of ANF is strongly dependent on its configuration setup. Inappropriate parameter settings of the ANF for interference removal may induce severe distortion to the correlation process. In addition, an effective mitigation will still introduce a vestigial signal distortion contributed by the residual unmitigated chirp and the ANF operation itself, being not negligible for high accuracy solutions. This paper addresses the detailed analysis for assessing the effects of interference mitigation by notch filtering. A bias compensation strategy is proposed, wherein for each Pseudo Random Noise (PRN) the biases due to the parameter settings of the notch filter are estimated and compensated. The impact of using the ANF operation on chirp signals at the acquisition and tracking stages of GNSS receivers is analyzed. On the basis of the three proposed metrics, the effects can be quantitatively estimated to depict a complete picture of the most influential parameters of the chirp and the ANF configurations, as well as the optimal achievable performance at the acquisition and tracking stages.

Index Terms—Interference Mitigation, Adaptive Notch Filter, Chirp, Interference Error Envelope, Notch Error Envelope, GNSS Receiver.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE extensive applications of positioning and navigation solutions based on the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) increasingly demand robustness of GNSS receiver performance. Disruptive effects can be induced to the signal processing stages of GNSS receivers due to the presence of Radio-Frequency Interference (RFI), leading to degraded estimation of Position, Velocity and Time (PVT) or eventually a complete denial of the receiver service [1]. Such interference threats rapidly expand with the increasing number

of wireless communication infrastructures that can potentially transmit signals at frequencies close to the allocated GNSS bands as unintentional disturbances [2] as well as the effect of natural interferences which are not negligible when dealing with high accuracy performance [3]. In addition, a more severe threat is posed by the Personal Privacy Devices (PPDs), widely known as jammers, which are used to intentionally broadcast powerful signals with carrier frequency varying over GNSS bands in a target area, in order to cause an outage of the GNSS based service [4] [5]. The widely explored pre-correlation techniques aim to detect and mitigate interference with advanced digital signal processing techniques before the correlation process performed in the GNSS receiver. Due to the various interference types, the mitigation methods are expected to customize for the specific interference characteristics.

Considering the extremely low power of the received GNSS signals, an efficient interference mitigation solution demands a good trade-off between the preservation of the useful GNSS signals and the effective cancellation of the interference. Different types of interference affect GNSS signals in different ways, causing distortion of the ranging code and affecting the correlation process.

Many pre-correlation approaches have been proposed so far in the literature based on the techniques in time-domain [6] [7], frequency-domain [8], time-frequency domain [9] and transformed domain [10] [11]. The adaptive filter techniques can be implemented for interference suppression [12], among which the Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) based Adaptive Notch Filter (ANF) is particularly appealing due to its low complexity and low computational load [13] [14]. The ANF is the evolution of the Notch Filter (NF) which is characterized by a passband frequency response that remains constant for the largest part of the frequency domain but it rejects a narrow portion of the spectrum in correspondence of the interference. The NF has been proved to be effective on the mitigation of Continuous Wave Interference (CWI) [13], Narrow Band Interference (NBI) [15] [16] and pulsed interference [17], thus it has been preferably implemented into the high-end GNSS receivers for interference removal. A more challenging scenario is the countermeasure for swept-frequency (chirp) jamming signals. With an additional adaptive block, the ANF is capable of tracking the frequency variation of the chirp signals [14]. Equivalent modifications on the adaptive block by employing Frequency Lock Loop (FLL) theory are further proposed [18] and extensively discussed [19] [20]. According to [21], the regular ANF and FLL-equivalent ANF architec-

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tures show comparable performance.

On the other hand, the procedure of mitigation operation itself may also bring not negligible distortion to the GNSS signals. The effects of the NF operation on the acquisition and tracking stages have been addressed in the literature by exploiting specific metrics for evaluation. In [13], the code distortion introduced by the NF operation at the acquisition stage in absence of interference is evaluated quantitatively by calculating the loss of Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) at the correlation output. Analysis shows the degradation of SNR due to the NF operation is related to the shift frequency and rejection bandwidth of the notch with respect to the code spectrum. Such SNR loss varies with different code structures but shows negligible difference for different Pseudo Random Noise (PRN). A further exploration on the effects at the tracking stage is conducted in [22] [23], and [24]. In [22] the bias and jitter caused by NF operation with different shift frequencies and rejection bandwidths in absence of interference are qualitatively estimated with a proposed metric called asymmetry coefficient. In [24] the effects of different NF methods on autocorrelation function distortion are estimated.

However, the analysis of the effects of NF in the signal processing stages of GNSS receivers is still far from being fully covered and this paper addresses additional topics to enrich and complete the investigation. The analysis in [13], [22] and [23] is implemented under the assumption that no interference exists, whereas the presence of interference makes the distortion analysis more complex. In fact, the code distortion is the result of combined effect of both the NF and the residual unmitigated interference. Another tricky problem is the analysis of the ANF effects for chirp signal removal. The parameters of the adaptive block that control the convergence capability of the ANF should be carefully tuned. Inappropriate parameter settings of the ANF would lead to unsuccessful chirp mitigation, as it will be shown in this paper.

The distortion analysis at the acquisition and tracking stages due to the ANF operation for the chirp signal removal has been preliminarily investigated in [21] and [25]. The metrics of α_{mean} , Interference Error Envelope (IEE) and code jitter are selected to quantitatively assess the distortion and thus to evaluate the ANF efficiency. This paper extends such preliminary results to a comprehensive analysis of the effects.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II is an introduction to the signal and system models. A description of the mitigation techniques is given in Section III. Section IV outlines the assessment tools for distortion analysis. Comparative analysis of two simulation scenarios are addressed in Section V and Section VI respectively. While the former provides an estimation of the distortion caused by the NF operation for CWI removal at the tracking stage, the latter extends the discussion to the effects of the ANF for chirp cancellation in the complete signal processing chain of GNSS receivers. Section VII draws the conclusions.

II. SIGNAL AND SYSTEM MODELS

A general scheme of a GNSS receiver is depicted in Fig. 1, where the GNSS signals are received at the antenna, further

down-converted to the Intermediate Frequency (IF), filtered and digitalized at the front-end. An additional pre-correlation mitigation unit is employed to implement advanced detection and mitigation techniques. In the signal processing chain of a GNSS receiver, the acquisition stage is designed to perform a rough estimation of the code delay and the Doppler frequency of the incoming GNSS signals, and the tracking stage is exploited to finalize the estimation progressively through tracking loops. PVT values are eventually obtained on the basis of the output at the tracking stage.

In a scenario where the interference is present, the received signals after the Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) at the front-end can be modeled as:

$$r[n] = \sum_{k=1}^N s_k[n] + \eta[n] + i[n] \quad (1)$$

where $r[n]$ is the received signal at IF, $s_k[n]$ is the GNSS signal collected from the k th satellite, $\eta[n]$ is the additive Gaussian noise, $i[n]$ is the interference and n is the discrete time index. $s_k[n]$ can be defined as

$$s_k[n] = A_k c_k(nT_s - \tau_k) h_k(nT_s - \tau_k) d_k(nT_s - \tau_k) \exp\{j2\pi(f_{IF} + f_d^k)nT_s + j\phi_k\} \quad (2)$$

where A_k is the signal amplitude, c_k is the spreading code, h_k is the subcarrier, d_k is the navigation data, T_s is the time sampling interval, τ_k is the code delay, f_{IF} is the intermediate frequency, f_d^k is the Doppler frequency and ϕ_k is the carrier phase.

The interference component $i[n]$ can be modeled differently according to the interference type. A detailed classification and description of the interference types is addressed in [1]. In this paper two specific types of interference, i.e. CWI and linear chirp are considered for the test scenarios. The value of Carrier-to-Interference ratio (C/I), i.e. the ratio between the power strength of the GNSS signal with respect to the interference power, will be used to characterize the different scenarios.

A complex CWI, represented as a spectral line in the frequency domain, can be defined as:

$$i_{cw}[n] = A_{cw} \exp\{j2\pi f_i n T_s + j\phi_i\} \quad (3)$$

where A_{cw} is the CWI amplitude, f_i is the CWI frequency and ϕ_i is the CWI phase.

A linear chirp is characterized by the linear variation of the carrier frequency over a frequency bandwidth named sweep range B_n within one chirp period T_p .

The linear chirp signal in one period T_p can be modeled as

$$i_{cp}[n] = A_{cp} \exp\left\{j2\pi f_0 n T_s + j2\pi v_s (n T_s)^2 / 2 + j\phi_{cp}\right\} \quad (4)$$

where A_{cp} is the chirp amplitude, f_0 is the starting frequency of the sweep range, v_s is the sweep rate, defined as $v_s = B_n/T_p$, and ϕ_{cp} is the chirp phase. The central frequency of the chirp can be obtained as $f_c = f_0 + B_n/2$.

Fig. 1: A general scheme of a GNSS receiver.

Fig. 2: Spectrogram of a GPS L1 signal interfered by a linear chirp, with $B_n = 16$ MHz, $T_p = 20$ μ s, $v_s = 0.8$ MHz/ μ s, $f_c = 0$ MHz and $C/I = -50$ dB.

The spectrogram of a GPS L1 signal interfered by a linear chirp is shown in Fig. 2 as an example. The values for B_n and T_p are the ones of a typical chirp signal broadcasted by a mass-market jammer as reported in [5].

III. MITIGATION TECHNIQUES

The theoretical model of the IIR based ANF has been proposed and extensively discussed in the literature [13] [14]. In general, the architecture of the ANF can be regarded as a combination of the notch filter and an additional adaptive block, that are briefly reviewed in the following.

A. Notch Filter

The one-pole notch filter can be employed to suppress complex CWI. As already addressed in [13], the transfer function of a one-pole notch filter is given by

$$H(z) = \frac{1 - z_0 z^{-1}}{1 - k_\alpha z_0 z^{-1}} \quad (5)$$

where $k_\alpha \in [0, 1)$ is the pole contraction factor regulating the width of the notch and z_0 is the zero of the transfer function to be placed at the frequency in correspondence of the interference. The relation between z_0 and the notch frequency f_{nf} can be expressed as

$$z_0 = \exp(j2\pi f_{nf} T_s) \quad (6)$$

where z_0 is forced to move on the unit circle. An ideal notch for the cancellation of CWI expressed in (3) is obtained when $f_{nf} = f_i$ with a very small rejection bandwidth, thus to preserve the most useful GNSS signals. According to [1], the 3 - dB attenuated bandwidth of the notch filter can be approximately calculated as

$$B_{3dB} \approx (1 - k_\alpha) f_s \pi / 10 \quad (7)$$

which indicates a larger k_α close to 1 leads to a smaller notch bandwidth, being f_s the sampling frequency.

The one-pole notch filter can be further extended to two-pole and multi-pole notch filters to suppress the real CWI with two or multiple spectral lines in the frequency domain [14].

B. Adaptive Block

In order to track the frequency span of the swept-frequency signals, adaptive techniques are proposed in [14] and [18], leading to two ANF architectures, denoted as the regular ANF and the FLL-equivalent ANF respectively. While the former estimates the frequency of the interfering signal through the stochastic gradient based technique, the latter employs FLL-based techniques.

In the regular ANF [14], z_0 is enabled to move in the complex plane and converge to the interference through a Least-Mean-Square (LMS) based iterative rule to progressively calculate z_0 at run-time

$$z_0[n] = z_0[n-1] - \mu[n] g(J[n]) \quad (8)$$

where $\mu[n]$ is the algorithm step, $J[n]$ is the cost function to be minimized and $g(\cdot)$ is the stochastic gradient of the cost function.

To properly obtain the adaptive algorithms, the transfer function (5) can be written as a cascade of Auto Regressive (AR) and Moving Average (MA) blocks and there are different ways to set the blocks [13] [18]. According to [18], the MA output is given by

$$y_m[n] = r[n] - z_0 r[n-1] \quad (9)$$

where $r[n]$ is the received interfered signal defined in (1).

The output of the filter $x_f[n]$ corresponding to (5) can be expressed as

$$x_f[n] = r[n] - z_0 r[n-1] + k_\alpha z_0 x_f[n-1] \quad (10)$$

and $x_r[n]$ is the output of the AR block, given by

$$x_r[n] = r[n] + k_\alpha z_0 x_r[n-1]. \quad (11)$$

As proposed in [14] and [18], the cost function in (8) can be either designed to minimize the expectation of the NF output energy as $J[n] = E\{|x_f[n]|^2\}$ or to minimize the expectation of the MA output energy as $J[n] = E\{|y_m[n]|^2\}$. $\mu[n]$ in (8) is the algorithm step [26], given by

$$\mu[n] = \frac{\delta}{E\{|x_r[n]|^2\}} \quad (12)$$

where $E\{|x_r[n]|^2\}$ is the expectation of AR output energy and δ controls convergence.

The activation of the ANF is determined by comparing the modulus of the averaged z_0 to a predefined threshold T_h . The value of T_h is selected based on the Interference-to-Noise ratio (I/N) considered harmful to the receiver. The averaged z_0 is given by

$$\hat{z}_0[n] = \alpha \hat{z}_0[n-1] + (1 - \alpha) z_0[n] \quad (13)$$

where α is the forgetting factor.

The performance of ANF is strongly dependent on the parameter settings. k_α (notch width) and δ (convergence capability) are the two most influential parameters to shape the ANF and are expected to be carefully tuned. A smaller rejection bandwidth (k_α close to 1) will preserve the most useful GNSS signals but will also bring the difficulty to the adaptive block to track the frequency variation. Inappropriate values of the parameters may lead to strong distortion to the useful signals, even more severe than the distortion caused by the interference, thus a good trade-off is always demanded.

IV. ASSESSMENT TOOLS FOR DISTORTION ANALYSIS

The distortion induced by the interference and the ANF operation on the ranging code can affect the result of the correlation process between the received signals and the local code replica. The assessment tools selected for the distortion analysis provide approaches to quantitatively estimate the impairment of the interference and the ANF operation at both the acquisition and tracking stages, by employing three metrics: peak-to-noise-floor ratio, code bias and code jitter. The methodology employed to assess these metrics is briefly described in the following sections.

A. Assessment of the Peak-to-noise-floor Ratio

In acquisition, the correlation peak of the Cross-Ambiguity Function (CAF) is searched and α_{mean} is defined as a way to measure the correlation peak-to-noise-floor ratio in [1], and it is given by

$$\alpha_{\text{mean}} = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{x_p}{E_i} \right) \quad (14)$$

Fig. 3: Open loop code discriminator.

where x_p is the correlation peak of CAF and E_i is the average of i off-peak correlation points in the search space.

The increasing power of the interference will lead to the loss of α_{mean} , thus causing an increasing probability of a false alarm during the acquisition process [1]. When ANF is implemented, the value of α_{mean} can also indicate the ANF efficiency with different parameter settings. The use of α_{mean} for ANF parameter optimization is proposed in [21], with the benefit of employing a metric easy to assess directly at the acquisition stage of a GNSS receiver.

B. Assessment of the Code Bias

In code tracking the Delay Lock Loop (DLL) discriminator (S-Curve) is exploited to measure the residual error between the estimated code delay and the true code delay of the incoming signal. The presence of interference and the ANF operation will affect not only the correlation process but also the output of the DLL discriminator.

The concept of IEE has been proposed and discussed in [27] [28] and it is based on an open loop code discriminator in the absence of noise to quantitatively measure the code biases with respect to one or more characteristics of the interfering signal (e.g. interference frequency and phase). The IEE is depicted as a plot of the maximum and minimum values of the ranging errors versus the chosen interference parameters.

In an open loop code discriminator as illustrated in Fig. 3, it is assumed that the Doppler frequency and the code delay are perfectly estimated in the in-phase and quadrature branches. The correlation is then performed between the incoming signal and the local early and late replicas, and correlation distortion is due to the interference and the ANF operation.

The receiver configuration can be adjusted in terms of discriminator function, correlator spacing and integration time. A coherent early-late discriminator function $R_{EL,C}$ is employed in [28], expressed as

$$R_{EL,C} = I_E - I_L \quad (15)$$

where I_E and I_L are the output of the early and late in-phase correlators.

Similarly, non-coherent discriminator function can be used for the evaluation. Many options of the non-coherent discriminator functions have been proposed [29] and there is a freedom to choose one for the investigation. The same discriminator

function $R_{EL,NC}$ has been considered for the bias and jitter analysis, given by

$$R_{EL,NC} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(I_E^2 + Q_E^2) - (I_L^2 + Q_L^2)}{(I_E^2 + Q_E^2) + (I_L^2 + Q_L^2)} \quad (16)$$

where Q_E and Q_L are the output of the early and late quadrature correlators.

As already demonstrated in [28], coherent and non-coherent discriminators lead to negligible difference on the IEE estimation, and the same also applies for different correlator spacing ($\Delta \leq 1$ chip). This finds explanation in the assumption of perfect Phase Lock Loop (PLL) and DLL, thus implying that the GNSS signal power is fully recovered in the in-phase branch only. This is true for the unfiltered signal, while in the case of one-pole notch filter, some GNSS signal power will be split also to the quadrature branch after the filtering operation, thus showing different results if a non-coherent discriminator is applied.

Without loss of generality, in this paper the IEE analysis has been entirely conducted considering only the coherent discriminator function in (15) and the applied methodology can be extended to different discrimination rules. Two code structures, i.e. Binary Phase Shift Keying (BPSK) and Binary Offset Carrier BOC (1,1) are simulated for the assessment of IEE, with integration time of 1 ms and 4 ms respectively.

C. Assessment of the Code Jitter

The IEE mainly reflects the bias induced at the zero-crossing point of the S-Curve, but such bias is not the only relevant effect. In this regard, as investigated in [28], in presence of CWI the S-Curve around the zero-crossing point shows to be still linear and parallel to the ideal one, i.e. the interference-free S-Curve. As the power of CWI increases, the S-Curve looks more deformed but is still in a regular shape, while in presence of a chirp signal and after the filtering operation, the S-Curve proves to be strongly distorted with irregular shape, as discussed later in Section VI. In other words, zero bias alone is not sufficient to guarantee a successful DLL convergence to the zero-crossing point if the S-Curve is severely distorted. Thus, the overall shape deformation of the S-Curve also should be considered as an extra assessment of linearity loss, in addition to the bias induced at the zero-crossing point.

In this regard, the code jitter is employed as the metric to quantitatively evaluate such overall shape deformation. It is obtained as the normalized standard deviation of the tracking error in the steady-state condition in presence of additive noise [30]. While the IEE tool provides an approach to evaluate the most influential characteristics of both the interference and the ANF configurations, the value of the code jitter can indicate the noisiness of the ranging errors and the filtering efficiency.

In this case, a closed loop DLL architecture is considered: the null-seeker structure is implemented to continuously seek the null at the output of the discriminator, in order to provide a fine estimation of code delay in presence of additive noise. The discriminator function $R_{EL,NC}$ expressed in (16) is used in the simulation scenarios, with spacing $\Delta = 1$ chip and integration time of 1 ms.

V. BIAS ANALYSIS: CWI VERSUS NF

The analysis first addresses the case of CWI and NF, based on the metric of IEE. This is an extension to the study on the IEE for CWI discussed in [27] and [28]. All the simulations are performed considering a digital version of the GNSS signals. The GNSS signal is generated by the N-FUELS Signal Simulation Tool [31]. A MATLAB[®]-based Software Defined Radio (SDR) GNSS receiver is used in order to implement the mitigation methods and analyze the performance [32].

A. S-Curve

In Fig. 4 the S-Curve is depicted as an example to demonstrate the possible distortion induced by CWI and NF operation. The zero-crossing point of the S-Curve for $\tau \in [-\frac{\Delta}{2}, \frac{\Delta}{2}]$ chip refers to the lock point of DLL at the tracking stage and the existence of a bias will lead to a ranging error in the estimated pseudorange. Line 1 in the figure shows the ideal S-Curve of a clean input GPS L1 signal, with the zero-crossing point located exactly at the zero delay. A noticeable bias is induced to the zero-crossing point when the signal is interfered by a CWI with carrier frequency centered at 0.5 MHz away from the GPS L1 carrier with $C/I = 0$ dB, as shown by line 2, whereas the overall shape of the S-Curve around the lock point still keeps parallel to the interference-free case represented by line 1.

Line 3 and line 4 illustrate the S-Curve distorted by narrow NFs with $k_\alpha = 0.99$ and $k_\alpha = 0.95$ respectively, in absence of interference. It can be observed that not only biases are introduced but also the slopes of the S-Curve around the lock point are different and no longer parallel to line 1. Furthermore, with $k_\alpha = 0.95$, the induced bias is even larger than the interfered case of line 2. This result clearly points out how it is important to activate the NF only when the presence of the interfering signal is detected.

Finally, the CWI described above is mitigated by means of an ideal NF with the same k_α indicated before and placed at the exact frequency of the CWI. Thus, line 5 and line 6 show the distorted S-Curve due to both the NF operation and the residual unmitigated CWI, with $k_\alpha = 0.99$ and $k_\alpha = 0.95$ respectively. Compared to line 3 and line 4, the biases at the zero-crossing point after the CWI mitigation exhibit negligible differences, thus proving that the CWI is efficiently mitigated and the remained biases are mainly due to the NF operation, while the contribution of the residual unmitigated CWI is nearly irrelevant. This means that in the presence of a weak CWI, as is the case, the NF operation may degrade performance more than the interference itself in the GNSS receivers, thus making the mitigation not so convenient. As a general observation, a good mitigation of the CWI by means of NF does not guarantee to nullify the bias, on the contrary a residual bias resulting from the combination of the filtering operation and the unfiltered interfering power can be observed.

Both CWI and NF operation can cause distortion of the S-Curve, as better explained hereafter by the analysis of the theoretical model.

According to [28], the coherent discriminator function (15) under interference can be written as:

Fig. 4: An example of the induced distortion on S-Curve by CWI and NF for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1).

$$R_{EL}^{si} [n] = R_E^{si} [n] - R_L^{si} [n] \quad (17)$$

where the superscript s and i stand for the GNSS signal component and the interference component respectively, being $R_E^{si} [n] = I_E$ and $R_L^{si} [n] = I_L$. In this regard, $R_{EL}^{si} [n]$ can be rewritten by splitting into two terms:

$$R_{EL}^{si} [n] = R_{EL}^s [n] + R_{EL}^i [n] \quad (18)$$

where the distorted discriminator function $R_{EL}^{si} [n]$ can be regarded as the sum of two components $R_{EL}^s [n]$ and $R_{EL}^i [n]$, which are respectively the ideal S-Curve and the induced distortion due to the interference. Under the assumption that the Doppler frequency and the code delay are perfectly estimated, the two terms can be modeled by simply employing the convolution theory

$$R_{EL}^s [n] = \frac{1}{NL} (c_E [n] - c_L [n]) * s_c [n] \quad (19)$$

$$R_{EL}^i [n] = \frac{1}{NL} (c_E [n] - c_L [n]) * i [n] \quad (20)$$

where N refers to the number of integration periods, L is the samples per code period and $*$ is convolution. $c_E [n]$ and $c_L [n]$ are the local early and late code replicas respectively. $s_c [n]$ is the code component of the input GNSS signal and $i [n]$ is the CWI.

The total bias at the zero-crossing point of the distorted discriminator function $R_{EL}^{si} [n]$ in (18) is then the sum of two components:

$$b_{EL}^{si} = b_{EL}^s + b_{EL}^i \quad (21)$$

where b_{EL}^s is a deterministic component with zero bias obtained from the ideal S-Curve $R_{EL}^s [n]$ and b_{EL}^i is the induced bias due to the distortion term $R_{EL}^i [n]$.

Similarly, the coherent discriminator function after the implementation of the NF can be written as the sum of two terms:

$$R_{EL}^{si,nf} [n] = R_{EL}^{s,nf} [n] + R_{EL}^{i,nf} [n] \quad (22)$$

where the superscript nf stands for the NF operation. Based on (19) and (20), $R_{EL}^{s,nf} [n]$ and $R_{EL}^{i,nf} [n]$ can be further modeled as

$$R_{EL}^{s,nf} [n] = \frac{1}{NL} (c_E [n] - c_L [n]) * s_c [n] * h_{nf} [n] \quad (23)$$

$$R_{EL}^{i,nf} [n] = \frac{1}{NL} (c_E [n] - c_L [n]) * i [n] * h_{nf} [n] \quad (24)$$

where $h_{nf} [n]$ is the discrete impulse response of the NF.

Finally, the total bias of the distorted discriminator function $R_{EL}^{si,nf} [n]$ in (22) after the implementation of the NF at the zero-crossing point can be written as

$$b_{EL}^{si,nf} = b_{EL}^{s,nf} + b_{EL}^{i,nf} \quad (25)$$

where $b_{EL}^{s,nf}$ is a deterministic component with bias obtained from the S-Curve $R_{EL}^{s,nf} [n]$ and $b_{EL}^{i,nf}$ is the induced bias due to the term $R_{EL}^{i,nf} [n]$.

As shown in Fig. 4, there are four types of S-Curve considered in different scenarios and each of them can be represented as one of the discriminator functions expressed above. The reference S-Curve (line 1) refers to the discriminator function $R_{EL}^s [n]$ in (19), with zero bias $b_{EL}^s = 0$. The S-Curve distorted by CWI (line 2) refers to the discriminator function $R_{EL}^i [n]$ in (18), with $b_{EL}^i = b_{EL}^i$. $R_{EL}^{s,nf} [n]$ in (23) and $R_{EL}^{i,nf} [n]$ in (22) are the discriminator functions distorted by the NF operation, respectively in absence of interference (line 3 and line 4) and in presence of the CWI (line 5 and line 6). The total bias $b_{EL}^{si,nf}$ in (25) is then contributed by both the NF operation and the residual interference. Furthermore, if the signals and the parameter settings of the NF are fixed, for each PRN the deterministic bias $b_{EL}^{s,nf}$ in (25) can be estimated and compensated. In fact, this bias is related to z_0 , k_α and PRN number. As a result of this compensation process, the contribution due to the residual unmitigated CWI after NF

Fig. 5: NEE for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1), with $\Delta = 1$ chip.

operation, i.e. the term $b_{EL}^{i,nf}$, can be isolated and evaluated. In addition, rather than code-domain compensation, the same filter could be applied to the replica code to compensate the phase distortion induced by the filter [26]. It is also possible to implement a zero-phase filter offline using a recursive filter twice both forward and backward in time [33].

B. Error Envelope

In order to extend the above analysis, the metric of IEE is further employed and implemented to estimate the induced bias of the S-Curve versus the variable characteristics of both CWI and NF. Similarly, the concept of IEE can be extended to assess the ranging errors due to the NF operation itself, in absence of interference. The most influential characteristics of the one-pole notch filter introduced in Section III are the notch frequency and the rejection bandwidth. In this regard, a plot of the ranging errors versus the notch shift frequency, with different values of the pole contraction factor k_α (i.e. different bandwidths of the notch), is depicted in Fig. 5. This type of error envelope affected by the NF operation only, without interference effects, for sake of clarity will be called as Notch Error Envelope (NEE).

As shown in Fig. 5, the largest bias due to the NF operation comes at $f_{nf} \sim 0$ MHz for all k_α and the ranging errors gradually reduce toward to zero with overshoot-like behavior. Furthermore, a narrower notch (k_α close to 1) only affects a small portion of the frequency bandwidths while a wider notch shows more severe influence on larger bandwidths of the code spectrum.

In the remainder of this work, the CWI is mitigated using an ideal NF, i.e. placing the notch at the true frequency of the CWI (i.e. $f_{nf} = f_i$) in order to ensure the most effective mitigation. For this analysis, several values of the notch rejection bandwidth have been considered. The ranging errors are then contributed by both the NF operation and the residual CWI. In Fig. 6 the error envelope for the filtered CWI as a function of the CWI phase and frequency is shown as an example, with $k_\alpha = 0.9$. In Fig. 7 the obtained maximum and

Fig. 6: Error envelope versus CWI phase and CWI shift frequency after NF mitigation for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1), with $k_\alpha = 0.9$.

minimum values of the ranging errors over all CWI phases versus the CWI shift frequency for different values of k_α are then depicted. It can be observed that the overall shape of the IEE for the filtered CWI is very similar to the NEE in Fig. 5, thus further confirming that the CWI is efficiently cancelled and the distortion induced by NF is by far dominant with respect to the residual unmitigated CWI.

As previously discussed, it is possible to estimate the deterministic term $b_{EL}^{s,nf}$ referring to the bias induced by the NF operation in (25), to achieve the compensated bias $b_{EL}^{i,nf}$ due to the residual unmitigated CWI. The compensation operation can be implemented for the IEE in Fig. 7 by subtracting the values of ranging errors in NEE as depicted in Fig. 5. Fig. 8 illustrates the compensated error envelope for CWI after NF mitigation as a function of CWI phase and shift frequency, with $k_\alpha = 0.9$. Fig. 9 presents then the extracted maximum and minimum values of the ranging errors. It can be observed that the compensated errors in Fig. 9 are very small, showing a symmetric trend which is similar to the IEE for CWI as shown in [28].

Different receiver configurations and code structures lead to different resilience to the impairment induced by the NF operation. In Fig. 10 it can be observed that with a smaller spacing of the discriminator the overall induced ranging error is reduced. Furthermore, a BOC (1,1) modulated signal shows more resilience to the narrow notch than BPSK when $f_{nf} \sim 0$ MHz as demonstrated in Fig. 11.

VI. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ON THE IMPAIRMENT: CHIRP VERSUS ANF

In the previous section a fixed frequency interference is considered to show the effects due to the NF. In this Section the assessment of the impairment induced by the chirp signal and the ANF operation is performed on the basis of the three metrics introduced in Section IV.

Fig. 7: IEE for CWI after NF mitigation for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1).

Fig. 8: Error envelope versus CWI phase and CWI shift frequency after NF mitigation and compensation process for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1), with $k_{\alpha} = 0.9$.

Fig. 9: IEE for CWI after NF mitigation and compensation process for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1).

A. Simulation Scenario

Digital linear chirp signals are simulated at baseband according to the parameters of the real chirp signals investigated in [5] and combined to the GPS L1 and Galileo E1b signals (without data) simulated by the N-FUELS at IF level. It is assumed that the sweep ranges of the simulated chirps are within the pass-bandwidth of the front-end. The 16 MHz bandwidth chosen for the jammer sweep range is justified by the fact that the high-end receivers may use wide front-end bandwidth to exploit all the signal components on L1/E1 bands (e.g. Time-Multiplexed BOC and Composite BOC) and to better characterize multipath and interference with appropriate signal processing. Thus, narrow band filtering effects due to the front-end which may distort the chirp pattern is not considered in this work. The definition of the parameters that characterize the chirp signals has been described in Section II and a full list of the simulation parameters is given in Table I.

B. α_{mean} Analysis

The evaluation process on the effect of ANF for chirp removal is carried out based on the α_{mean} at the acquisition stage of the receiver. As reference the value of α_{mean} in an interference-free scenario is first calculated as 47.9 dB whereas α_{mean} for the scenario suffering the chirp signal with parameters described in Table I is 20.3 dB, leading to an unsuccessful acquisition. The loss of α_{mean} between the interference-free case and the interfered case can be regarded as the impairment due to the interference. The ANF is then implemented for the chirp cancellation with different parameter settings. The degradation of α_{mean} after the ANF operation is caused by both the ANF operation and the residual unmitigated interference, and this effect can be quantitatively evaluated by comparing it against to the interference-free case.

Additionally, the ANF efficiency is also reflected by comparing the values of α_{mean} with different parameter settings and in this way an optimization procedure can be performed.

TABLE I: Simulation setup

Simulation Parameters	Units	For Bias Analysis	For α_{mean} and Jitter Analysis	
Receiver Configuration	Sampling frequency (f_s)	MHz	49.104	49.104
	Intermediate Frequency (IF)	MHz	0	0
	Spacing (Δ)	chip	0.25, 0.5, 1	1
	Coherent integration time	ms	1, 4	1
	Non-coherent integration time	ms	/	1
GPS L1 Signal	PRN	/	1	1
	Power (P_{L1})	dBW	0	-157
	Carrier-to-Noise ratio (C/N_0)	dB - Hz	noise free	55
Galileo E1b Signal	PRN	/	1	/
	Power (P_{E1})	dBW	0	/
	Carrier-to-Noise ratio (C/N_0)	dB - Hz	noise free	/
Chirp Signal	Power (P_{cp})	dBW	0, 10, 20, 30	-107
	Sweep range (B_n)	MHz	4, 8, 12, 16	16
	Sweep period (T_p)	μs	6, 10, 20, 33	20
	Sweep rate (v_s)	MHz/ μs	0.48, 0.8, 1.6, 2.7	0.8
	Central frequency (f_c)	MHz	[0 \div 10] (spaced of 1 kHz)	0
	Chirp phase (ϕ_{cp})	rad	[0 \div 2π] (spaced of $\pi/5$)	0
	Carrier-to-Interference ratio (C/I)	dB	-30, -20, -10, 0	-50

Fig. 10: NEE for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1), with $k_\alpha = 0.99$ and different discriminator spacing.

Fig. 11: NEE for BOC (1,1), with $\Delta = 1$ chip.

As introduced in Section III, k_α and δ are the two most influential parameters to regulate the performance of the ANF and demand for a good trade-off. In Fig. 12 the values of α_{mean} with different k_α and δ are presented. The choice of δ is based on the empirical values and k_α changes between 0 and 1, representing different rejection bandwidths of the notch. The threshold T_h and the forgetting factor α in (13) are fixed to $T_h = 0.7$ and $\alpha = 0.9$. A direct picture of the optimal performance achievable by the ANF for chirp removal is illustrated. It can be seen that inappropriate parameter settings may directly lead to a significant loss of α_{mean} , causing an unsuccessful acquisition, whereas proper choices can reduce the loss of α_{mean} after the ANF operation. In the simulated scenario, the best parameter settings of k_α and δ is $k_\alpha = 0.9$ and $\delta = 0.1$ and these parameters can be tuned and continuously optimized based on the value of α_{mean} . The optimized zone for the choices of k_α and δ is to fix k_α between 0.8 and 0.9, and δ between 0.05 and 0.1. In order to finalize more precise parameter settings, other variable parameters besides k_α and δ can also be tuned based on the metric. According to the investigation in [21], the threshold T_h and the forgetting factor α do not show obvious influence to maximize the value of α_{mean} , compared to the effects of k_α and δ . The proposed method for parameter optimization can also fit the FLL-equivalent ANFs [21]. Although the value of α_{mean} is significantly recovered by the optimized ANF, there is still a noticeable loss compared to the interference-free case. This is due to the vestigial signal distortion introduced by the ANF operation and the residual unmitigated interference, which cannot be avoided.

C. Bias Analysis

The bias analysis addressed in Section V for CWI and NF is hereafter extended to chirp signals and ANF. The complexity of both the chirp and ANF models makes the estimation of the induced bias with respect to the variable characteristics more complex. A starting point is to evaluate the effects of the chirp signal on the discriminator function with different

Fig. 12: k_α and δ trade-off based on α_{mean} , with $B_n = 16$ MHz, $T_p = 20 \mu s$ and $C/I = -50$ dB.

Fig. 14: Error envelope for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1) versus chirp phase and chirp central frequency, with $B_n = 16$ MHz, $T_p = 20 \mu s$ and $C/I = 0$ dB.

Fig. 13: S-Curve for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1) distorted by a linear chirp, with $B_n = 16$ MHz, $T_p = 20 \mu s$ and $f_c = 1$ MHz.

characteristics. In this regard, the S-Curve distorted by a linear chirp over 1 ms, i.e. 50 chirp periods in total with $T_p = 20 \mu s$ in this case, is illustrated in Fig. 13 as an example. The presence of a linear chirp not only leads to a bias at the zero-crossing point, but also an overall shape deformation of the S-Curve. Differently from the case of CWI, where a more regular shape deformation appears as the power of CWI increases, the shape deformation due to the linear chirp is irregular and difficult to predict.

In order to obtain the IEE for the linear chirp signal, the ranging errors over all possible chirp phases versus chirp central frequency are depicted in Fig. 14. The IEE is then achieved as a plot of the extracted maximum and minimum values of the ranging errors over all chirp phases versus chirp central frequency. The typical parameters of the chirp signal are selected to estimate the effects of the characteristics on the generation of IEE. In Fig. 15 the influence of the power of the chirp on the IEE is demonstrated by choosing three different

power levels. It can be observed that the overall level of the IEE grows as the chirp power increases but still keeps a similar trend for different power levels. The overall shape of the IEE for the chirp signal fluctuates significantly as f_c increases when the chirp bandwidth is fully or partially covering the main lobe of the code spectrum, gradually reducing toward to zero for high f_c where the chirp bandwidth only affects the side lobes. Although the IEE for the chirp signal is quite different from the IEE for CWI in [28] and it looks irregular, the maximum and minimum values of the ranging errors still show to be approximately symmetric. Furthermore, the overall values of the ranging errors are much smaller than the case of IEE for CWI in the case of $C/I = 0$ dB. In Fig. 16, the sweep range of the chirp varies and the most influential effect on the envelope for each B_n appears at different f_c . For instance, a large B_n shows continuous effects on a wide range of the shift frequency while a narrow B_n only affects a small portion, depending on the portion it covers within the main lobe of the code spectrum. However, it seems that with a medium sweep rate ($v_s = 0.8$ MHz/ μs), a narrow B_n produce the largest errors in terms of IEE maximum values. In addition, the sweep rate is also considered as an interesting characteristic to investigate. The sweep rate is inversely proportional to the sweep period if B_n is fixed. Four different v_s are selected on the basis of the real chirp parameters described in [5], namely slow ($v_s = 0.48$ MHz/ μs), medium ($v_s = 0.8$ MHz/ μs), fast ($v_s = 1.6$ MHz/ μs) and rapid ($v_s = 2.7$ MHz/ μs). In Fig. 17, the IEE reflects that a slower v_s brings more severe impact on the IEE and the overall envelope decreases as the sweep rate increases.

Fig. 18 demonstrates the induced ranging errors with different discriminator spacing under the influence of a medium chirp signal. As already observed in Fig. 10, the overall ranging error reduces for smaller spacing of the discriminator, thus demonstrating more resilience to the chirp signal. The same trend can be noticed in Fig. 19, where the BOC (1,1)

Fig. 15: IEE for the linear chirp signal for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1) with different C/I , with $B_n = 16$ MHz and $T_p = 20 \mu s$.

Fig. 17: IEE for the linear chirp signal for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1) with different v_s , with $B_n = 16$ MHz and $C/I = -20$ dB.

Fig. 16: IEE for the linear chirp signal for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1) with different B_n , with $v_s = 0.8$ MHz/ μs and $C/I = -20$ dB.

Fig. 18: IEE for the linear chirp signal for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1) with different spacing, with $B_n = 16$ MHz, $T_p = 20 \mu s$ and $C/I = -20$ dB.

modulated signal exhibits even further reduced errors if compared to the BPSK.

The ANF is then implemented to mitigate the chirp signal and the effects on the IEE are investigated. In order to separately analyze the effect induced by the two main parameters, i.e. k_α and δ , the adaptive block is disabled and the one-pole NF is fed with the true z_0 at run-time, instead of calculating z_0 according to (8). In this way, an ideal frequency tracking capability of the ANF is assumed, so that the only impact to the IEE is due to the parameter k_α . The IEE for the linear chirp after the ideal ANF is shown in Fig. 20. Two k_α are selected as exemplary values. The resulting ranging errors, after an ideal chirp mitigation, are caused by both the NF operation and the residual unmitigated chirp. It can be noticed that the overall level of IEE decreases significantly and is no longer symmetric, confirming how an

effective mitigation is the dominant contribution compared to the residual chirp. However, when $f_c \sim 8$ MHz, the effectiveness of the mitigation operation decreases. This can be explained by considering the transient time of the ANF in correspondence of the frequency discontinuity between two chirp repetitions. As illustrated in Fig. 21, the ANF is not activated during the transient time and a small portion of the chirp remained unfiltered at the lower part of the chirp sweep range. When $f_c \sim 8$ MHz and $B_n = 16$ MHz in the case, the remaining unfiltered chirp partially covers the main lobe of the code spectrum, leading to an increasing impact.

At last, the interfered signal is filtered by the ANF with different parameter settings of k_α and δ , with fixed $T_h = 0.7$ and $\alpha = 0.9$. In Fig. 22, the IEE after ANF mitigation with three different parameter settings is depicted. All of the three cases show effective mitigation with significant reduction of

Fig. 19: IEE for the linear chirp signal for BOC (1,1) with different spacing, with $B_n = 16$ MHz, $T_p = 20 \mu\text{s}$ and $C/I = -20$ dB.

Fig. 21: Residual unmitigated chirp after ANF operation, with $B_n = 16$ MHz, $T_p = 20 \mu\text{s}$, and $C/I = -20$ dB.

Fig. 20: IEE for CWI after ideal ANF operation for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1).

Fig. 22: IEE for the linear chirp for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1) after ANF operation, with $B_n = 16$ MHz, $T_p = 20 \mu\text{s}$ and $C/I = -20$ dB.

the overall envelope. The IEE trends are similar to the ones in Fig. 20, showing a clear asymmetry between maximum and minimum values and higher errors for $f_c \sim 8$ MHz. Comparing the IEE in Fig. 20 and Fig. 22, both of the two cases are with $k_\alpha = 0.8$ and $k_\alpha = 0.9$, thus the difference is induced by the different frequency tracking capability. While the former has the ideal frequency tracking capability, the latter is limited by δ . It can be seen in Fig. 23 that after the ANF operation both the bias at the zero-crossing point and the overall shape deformation of the S-Curve are reduced. It is worth noticing that $f_c = 1$ MHz has been chosen since at this central frequency the error is relatively large as shown in Fig. 22.

As already observed for the CWI, also for a chirp signal, the ANF could induce a more severe distortion than the interference itself in case of inappropriate parameter settings. In addition, as the receiver configuration (e.g. Δ), the charac-

teristics of the chirp signal (e.g. P_{cp} , B_n , T_p and f_c) and the ANF parameters (e.g. k_α and δ) change, the distortion on the S-Curve and the error envelope could be very different.

D. Jitter Analysis

The jitter analysis is based on the same simulation setup used for the α_{mean} analysis at the acquisition stage as reported in Subsection VI-B. As reference the code jitter in scenarios with and without interference are respectively calculated as 2.13 m and 0.42 m. The difference between these two values can quantitatively reflect the impairment due to the chirp signal at the tracking stage.

In Fig. 24 the plot of code jitter expressed in meters as a function of k_α and δ is depicted. It can be observed that the value of code jitter differs significantly as the parameters change. A smaller value of the code jitter indicates a more

Fig. 23: S-Curve distortion after ANF operation for BPSK (GPS L1, PRN 1), with $B_n = 16$ MHz, $T_p = 20 \mu\text{s}$, $f_c = 1$ MHz and $C/I = -20$ dB.

effective chirp mitigation, with less induced bias and overall deformation of the S-Curve. Thus the optimized configuration for ANF can be obtained with k_α fixed between 0.8 and 0.9 and δ between 0.05 and 0.1 (see the light blue and orange plots). In particular, the combination $k_\alpha = 0.8$ and $\delta = 0.05$ results in a code jitter close to 0.60 m, showing the optimal performance achievable after the ANF operation. Based on the value of code jitter, it can be seen that even after the optimized filtering operation, the residual error is not negligible if compared to the interference-free case.

Similar to the use of α_{mean} , the metric of code jitter can also indicate the ANF efficiency at the tracking stage thus to optimize the parameter configurations. Furthermore, comparing Fig. 12 and Fig. 24, the two metrics at two signal processing stages lead to similar optimized configurations for the ANF. It seems to indicate that a good trade-off between k_α and δ can maximize both the acquisition and tracking performance along the signal processing chain based on the proposed metrics. This can help to find the optimal configuration for the ANF.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has addressed the problem of the impact of the ANF operation for chirp removal in the signal processing stages of GNSS receivers. As already extensively discussed, the performance of the ANF is strongly dependent on its configuration setup. Inappropriate parameter settings of the ANF can bring severe distortion to the correlation process, leading to an outage of the receiver service. Three metrics have been proposed as assessment tools to quantitatively evaluate the effects.

The investigation first goes to the bias analysis in the case of NF for CWI cancellation. NEE is proposed as the metric to quantitatively estimate the impairment merely by the NF operation at the tracking stage. Similar to the IEE, the NEE is a plot of ranging errors versus the parameters that regulate the NF performance, namely the rejection bandwidth and

Fig. 24: k_α and δ trade-off based on code jitter, with $B_n = 16$ MHz, $T_p = 20 \mu\text{s}$ and $C/I = -50$ dB.

the frequency of the notch. Although both the interference and the NF operation can separately affect the S-Curve with an induced bias at the zero-crossing point, the mechanism behind it is different. This is reflected in the different shapes of the IEE and the NEE as illustrated in Section V. Good mitigation of CWI by means of a NF does not guarantee zero code biases. On the contrary, a residual bias resulting from the combination of the filtering operation and the unfiltered residual interference can be observed, up to tens of meters depending on interference frequency and other parameters. When CWI is efficiently cancelled, then the distortion and biases caused by notch filtering are dominant with respect to the residual unmitigated interference. Additionally, a further bias compensation process is proposed that can be performed by excluding the NEE for each PRN. The IEE after compensation process is isolated from the deterministic notch filtering effects.

A more complex scenario is the comparative analysis of the impact of the ANF for chirp removal. The proposed three metrics are employed to assess the effects at both the acquisition stage and the tracking stage. The use of α_{mean} can depict a direct picture of the optimal performance achievable with different configurations of the ANF at the acquisition stage thus the optimized zone for parameter settings can be obtained. Inappropriate configuration setup may cause severe effects to the correlation process and lead to significant loss of α_{mean} . Therefore it provides an instrument to estimate the impairment due to the ANF operation by considering the loss of α_{mean} compared to the interference-free case.

The investigation is further carried out at the tracking stage by using the metrics of IEE and code jitter. The roles of the two metrics are different. The use of IEE aims to estimate the maximum distortions versus the variable characteristics to have a more comprehensive understanding on the most influential parameters of the chirp (e.g. P_{cp} , B_n , T_p and f_c) and the ANF (e.g. k_α and δ) at the tracking stage. However, due to the fact that the S-Curve may be irregularly distorted by the chirp

signal, the overall shape deformation of the S-Curve is also taken into account by estimating the code jitter. Based on the IEE the plot of ranging errors versus the variable parameters of the chirp and the ANF is depicted. Similar to the use of α_{mean} , the optimal achievable performance on the basis of code jitter can be directly obtained. The impairment due to the ANF operation can be assessed by comparing the value of code jitter to the interference-free case. In addition, it seems indicating that one good configuration setup for the ANF can maximize both the acquisition and tracking performance in GNSS receivers. This needs to be verified on other types of chirp signals and receiver configurations. For instance, a performance comparison of different discriminator architectures, both coherent and non-coherent, could be performed in the next future, in order to find the best tracking algorithms to be used when the ANF is performed.

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